

ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL AND UNIVERSAL SPIRITUAL VALUES

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the issue of values, which is one of the urgent problems of today. The essence and uniqueness of values, their types in terms of content and volume are scientifically explained in it. The article also deeply analyzes the vast spiritual, cultural and political experience accumulated by our people over the centuries, the valuable ideas of our ancestors in this regard, and the unique values ingrained in our lives.

Key words: value, national value, universal value, religion, religious tolerance, conscience, faith, belief, ideology.

INTRODUCTION

Universal values are not some separate aspect of human spiritual and social perfection, separated from others. Universal values are a generalized expression of national and regional values. Universal values are formed and developed on the basis of the values specific to all humanity, they also serve the convergence and development of all national values. When we say "value", we should understand the set of phenomena of nature and society that are important for people and humanity, serve the interests and goals of the nation, people and social groups and are therefore valued and appreciated by them [1].

Value is a dear and honorable, sacred and respected idea and principle, heritage and wealth, attitude and blessings for every person, family and community, nation and people. These are called values. By values, we understand the traditions and customs that have been formed for thousands of years, have taken a firm place in people's lives and inner world, are not reflected in any official documents, but are followed by all, and are absorbed in the blood of people. In other words, as long as there is a human being, as long as there is a nation, the signs and characteristics that represent this nation, which have risen to a sacred level over the centuries, live together with it [2].

"Values are a complex of people, relations, situations, material things and spiritual wealth that are important to people, attention, respect, influence in society" [3]. Although this description of values clearly expresses its essence, it is distinguished from other definitions by its scientific nature among the definitions given to values. Therefore, society, which is the most general community of mankind, is the creator and maintainer of universal values. Loyalty to the ideals of humanity, striving for the stability of democracy, social justice everywhere, preventing the violation of human rights, protecting the struggles of all peoples for national independence, calling people for friendship, cooperation and sympathy, trying to establish peace and tranquility everywhere, keeping the environment clean are aspects of universal human values that are gaining great importance today. These values include new aspects in the development of science, technology, culture, social production relations, democracy, legislation, and the achievements in the stabilization of justice acquired by all mankind. does. Allowing any retreats, national limitations and indolence in this regard can lead to extremely large losses. Universal values will have the desired effect only when they are connected with local conditions, opportunities, and historical traditions. Regional values are closely connected with universal values. This set of values is found in countries and people who lived and worked in similar conditions and had

a similar history. These values are still very important today.

The people of Central Asia have established close economic and political relations with each other for thousands of years. The fact is that their living conditions, language, culture, religion, and customs are close to each other has led to the formation of many regional values. Although these values are slightly different in different places, they are close in essence. Hospitality, childishness, close neighborliness, respect for elders, respect for children, close relations with relatives and friends, generosity, distinguishing between honest and illegal are the characteristics of the peoples of Central Asia. are spiritual qualities common to all. Although the traditions of hospitality are common throughout our region, they differ from place to place.

Respecting the elderly and parents is also a unique high spiritual wealth of the peoples of Central Asia. Elderly people are people who have seen a lot, can give advice in everything with intelligence, and can have a great educational influence on young people. Respecting the elderly, learning from them, learning life experience is trying to find new opportunities for spiritual growth. Respecting parents, listening to their words and advice is also a great moral value. A parent never sees evil in his child. Since they see many hardships and eases in life, they think about their children's prospects more than them. Sometimes the advice of parents is more difficult for incompetent children. This is the result of not knowing life, looking lightly at various processes of life. Children understand the value of parents only after they become parents themselves. During this period, they miss out on many opportunities for spiritual growth. Therefore, one should never forget the habit of respecting parents, which is a great moral value.

Respect for parents is found in all nations of the world. But in our region, respect for this value is more important than in other places. Helping each other in building houses, repairing houses, patting the heads of orphans and widows, relatives and relatives taking them under their protection not allowing it to be lost

is also a characteristic value of all the peoples of our region.

Another regional value of great social and educational importance is public opinion. Public opinion is an expression of closeness and mutual respect between people, and it is a value that can be widely used.

One of the most important types of values is national values. National values coexist with universal and regional values. Universal and regional values include many aspects of national values. National values will have the opportunity to develop and improve under the influence of universal and regional values. The dialectical relationship between them is one of the important factors in the development of world civilization.

The formation and development of national values is connected with each nation's unique history, language, culture, moral and psychological qualities, living conditions, lifestyle, and production activities. Each form of national values can be properly understood only through a deep study of the specific features of its long historical development.

As long as the nation exists, the importance of national values does not decrease at all. The spiritual convergence of nations does not reduce, but expands, the possibilities of development and implementation of national values. In general, national values are one of the main criteria that determine the essence of each nation, its independent socio-ethnic unity. Of course, changes in the social structure of the nation, closer relations between different peoples serve to grow and expand national values. But it continues to form in new conditions, based on new demands and needs. The values that are formed in new situations will have the opportunity to be absorbed into life more widely and faster only when they absorb the aspects of nationality.

The importance of national consciousness and sense of national unity are great for every nation to develop its values and follow them. Only people who are deprived of national spirit and spirituality can have a nihilistic attitude towards their

language, history, and traditions. If such a situation expands under the influence of certain policies, an extremely dangerous situation will arise for the unity and development of the nation.

Despite the strong ideological pressure that lasted for a long time, the people of Uzbekistan managed to preserve their historical and cultural values and unique traditions that have been passed down from generation to generation [4].

Of course, every nation should not be stuck in the shell of its national values. If you follow such a path, the pace of the nation's development will slow down.

National limitation and national independence have never been a factor of spiritual and social maturity. Studying the values of other nations has always been one of the factors of development.

No matter how close the values are to each other and influence each other, national values remain the main path and criterion of spiritual maturity for every nation. The good traditions and rituals of a nation can take root in the life of that nation only when they correspond to the spirit of another nation, its national spiritual needs and requirements.

National values are not some immutable phenomenon. Improvement of social, economic, and spiritual life related to the development of the nation, changes in living and working conditions will create an opportunity for the development of national values.

Along with universal, regional, national values, there are also religious values. Religious values are also formed based on the demands and needs of the society in certain historical periods and conditions.

Religious values are not some separate area of universal, regional values, sharply separated from others.

It is known that any religion did not appear in isolation from life requirements, living conditions and needs. The origin of all religions was caused by the social, political, ideological conditions of certain historical periods, and the needs

connected with them. The reasons for the origin of religions should be sought from social life itself. Events and needs of real life become religious only when their essence and causes are connected with the will of divine forces.

The international community recognizes and acknowledges that our ancient and beautiful land was one of the cradles of not only Eastern, but also world civilization. The role of secular and religious sciences, especially the religion of Islam, which has become an integral part of universal civilization and culture, is incomparable. Respected President Sh. Mirziyoev says about this: "It is the honorable duty of each of us to preserve and appreciate our sacred religion, which embodies our ancient values and moral qualities. Islam means understanding the truth, it encourages people to do good deeds, calls each of us to goodness and peace, teaches to be a real person. We strongly condemn those who try to use the religion of Islam for the purposes of violence and bloodshed, and we will never compromise with them. We always protect our holy religion" [5]. That is why the services of the great scholars who were born and matured in our motherland in raising the knowledge related to Islamic religion and spiritual values to the highest level in history gives us great pride and honor.

During the formation of the Islamic religion, Muhammad, peace be upon him, gave a divine touch to many customs, rituals, moral and legal standards common among the Arab tribes and made them an integral part of the new religion. Many values of Arab behavior, manners and morals, family and tribal relations became part of the Islamic religion. A great place is reserved for moral and legal values in the Qur'an and hadiths. In particular, there is no doubt that the moral standards described in hadiths have a positive effect on human maturity. Many moral qualities of Muhammad, his attitude towards his family, children, and friends are recorded in the hadiths and have become educational values. All moral and legal values revealed in hadiths and poetic judgments can be widely used as an educational factor even today.

The independence of Uzbekistan and the abolition of the ideological rule of the autocratic regime made it possible to approach religious values in a new way. Many religious rituals have been restored, and citizens have started to perform rituals and customs related to their religious beliefs without any obstacles. At the same time, the patriotism towards Uzbekistan among our citizens of different nationalities has started to take root.

Patriotism is not only taking up arms and fighting for the Motherland. It is also patriotism to acquire the skills of science, culture, and practical work and to spread the love of the motherland to the world. Many of our great compatriots spread the reputation of their country to the world by acquiring and developing the skills of science, culture, and high applied arts.

Independent Uzbekistan needs true patriots and devoted youth. We have a lot of national values that are the basis for educating such young people. Their widespread use is of great importance.

Independence-related patriotism is not only a deep understanding of the historical past. At this point, it is necessary to know the current tasks facing our country and the possibilities of fulfilling them, and to show examples of zeal and selflessness in this regard. The transition to market relations has also strengthened the qualities of personal desire and self-interest in people. The cases of activities based on the idea "Die for yourself, orphan" are increasing. However, no matter how strong the sentiment of personal interest is, in such a responsible and historical turning point as it is now, the issues of the Motherland and Independence cannot be left in the shade. Only if the Motherland develops freely and rises to the highest levels of world development, a person can quickly carry out work related to his own interest. Values related to national educational traditions are extremely important in the formation of ecological culture. In Uzbek families, children were taught to sweep the street, clean the yard, sprinkle water, plant and care for trees from a young age. Not polluting the water and not throwing garbage everywhere has

become a great national value. These values can also be a great educational factor in the current situation, when the ecological situation in our country has become very difficult.

We also have great historical traditions in educating Uzbek girls in the spirit of hard work and humility. Honor, faith, and the habit of maintaining virginity are also great national values.

The fact that the issue of values occupies a large place in philosophical teachings is also required by these aspects of them.

The educational system of the Uzbek people has its own characteristics, which have been formed historically, due to which our youth are distinguished from the youth of other nations. For example, a father and mother are ashamed of some shameful behavior of their child and say: You put me in the isnad, my dear. How do I look at the country now? I can't leave the neighborhood. At the root of these words is the sacred concept of protecting one's own reputation and the reputation of the family. Honesty and integrity are also important values.

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